

Phenylpropionic Acids. Part XI.¹ Factors Governing the Mode of Self-Condensation of Arylpropionic Acids

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3-Halogeno-, 3-halogeno-4-methyl and 3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenylpropionic acids are converted with acetic anhydride into a mixture of 6-halogeno-, and 8-halogeno substituted 1-phenylnaphthalene-2, 3-dicarboxylic anhydrides in different proportions. The structure of these anhydrides was established by spectroscopic methods, and the factors governing the mode of self-condensation are discussed.

I*N a previous publication,*² it was shown that whereas 3-chloro- and 3-iodo-4-methoxyphenylpropionic acids gave, when refluxed with acetic anhydride a mixture of the corresponding 6- and 8-halogeno-7-methoxy-1-(3'-halogeno-4'-methoxyphenyl) naphthalene-2, 3-dicarboxylic anhydrides, in which the latter was obtained in traces, 3-bromo-4-methoxyphenylpropionic acid, gave a mixture of 6-bromo-, and 8-bromo-7-methoxy-1-(3'-bromo-4'-methoxyphenyl) naphthalene-2, 3-dicarboxylic anhydrides in nearly equal proportions. This abnormal result urged the authors to extend the study to clarify the factors governing the self-condensation of 3-substituted and 3, 4-disubstituted phenylpropionic acids.

Experimental

All melting points are not corrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were measured on a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in cyclohexane were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 4000A spectracord.

3-Bromo- and 3-iodo-4-methylbenzaldehyde. Bromine (8.0 g) or iodine powder (15 g) was added to a well stirred mixture of *p*-tolualdehyde (6.5 g), silver sulphate (16.5 g), and 80% sulphuric acid (40 ml) at room temperature and at 50°-60°, respectively. Stirring was continued for 3 hr. and the cold solution poured on ice. The precipitated product was purified by stirring with sodium sulphite, extracted with ether, and washed with sodium carbonate solution. **3-Bromo-4-methylbenzaldehyde** (6.5 g) had m.p. 52°-3° (from light petroleum, b.p. 40°-60°) (Found: C, 48.3; H, 3.7; Br, 40.8%). C_8H_7BrO requires: C, 48.2; H, 3.5; Br, 40.2%. **3-Iodo-4-methylbenzaldehyde** (6.5 g) had m.p. 112°-4° (from ethanol) (Found: C, 39.0; H, 3.2; I, 51.15%). C_8H_7IO requires: C, 39.0; H, 2.8; I, 51.6%.

Preparation of Cinnamic Acids. The mixture of the corresponding aldehyde (3.0 g; 1 mol.), malonic acid (1.1 mol.) absolute ethanol (15 ml), and pyridine (0.5 ml) was heated on a boiling-water-bath for 6 hr, and the reaction product was worked up as usual. **3-Bromo-4-methyl-cinnamic acid** (3.0 g) had m. p.

201°-2° (from benzene) (Found: C, 49.9; H, 3.7; Br, 34.6). $C_{10}H_9BrO_2$ requires: C, 49.8; H, 3.7; Br, 33.2%. **3-Iodo-4-methyl-cinnamic acid** (3.0 g) had m.p. 188°-90° (from toluene) (Found: C, 41.15; H, 3.1; I, 44.1). $C_{10}H_9IO_2$ requires: C, 41.65; H, 3.1; I, 44.1%. **3-Fluoro-4-methoxy-cinnamic acid** (3.0 g) had m.p. 213°-5° (from glacial acetic acid) (Found: C, 60.95; H, 4.7; F, 9.5). $C_{10}H_9FO_3$ requires: C, 61.2; H, 4.6; F, 9.7%.

The corresponding methyl or ethyl esters were prepared by refluxing the acids (3.0 g) with absolute ethanol (or methanol) (30 ml) for 3 hr. **Ethyl 3-bromo-cinnamate** (2.8 g) had m. p. 125°-7° (from light petroleum, b.p. 60°-80°) (Found: C, 52.0; H, 4.6; Br, 31.35). $C_{11}H_{11}BrO_2$ requires: C, 51.75; H, 4.3; Br, 31.35%. **Methyl 3-iodocinnamate** (2.8 g) had m.p. 55°-7° (from light petroleum, b.p. 60°-80°) (Found: C, 41.5; H, 3.3; I, 43.5). $C_{10}H_9IO_2$ requires: C, 41.7; H, 3.1; I, 44.1%. **Ethyl 3-bromo-4-methyl-cinnamate** (2.8 g) had m.p. 49°-50° (from light petroleum b.p. 40°-60°) (Found: C, 53.3; H, 5.0; Br, 30.9). $C_{12}H_{13}BrO_2$ requires C, 53.5; H, 4.3; Br, 29.75%. **Ethyl 3-iodo-4-methylcinnamate** (2.8 g) had m.p. 73°-5° (from light petroleum, b.p. 60°-80°) (Found: C, 45.25; H, 4.3; I, 41.3). $C_{12}H_{13}IO_2$ requires: C, 45.6; H, 4.1; I, 40.2%. **Ethyl 3-fluoro-4-methoxycinnamate** (2.8 g) had m. p. 34°-5° (from light petroleum, b.p. 40°-60°) (Found: C, 64.6; H, 5.9; F, 8.6). $C_{12}H_{13}FO_3$ requires: C, 64.7; H, 5.8; F, 8.8%.

β -Aryl- α : β -dibromopropionic Esters. A stirred cold solution of the above cinnamic esters (0.01 mol) in chloroform (30 ml) was brominated by portionwise addition of bromine (0.01 mol) in chloroform (10 ml). After standing for one hr, the chloroform was evaporated spontaneously at room temperature. **Ethyl α : β -dibromo- β -(3-bromophenyl) propionate** (4.0 g) had m.p. 63°-4° (from light petroleum, b.p. 40°-60°) (Found: C, 32.20; H, 2.65; Br, 59.75). $C_{11}H_{11}Br_2O_2$ requires: C, 31.90; H, 2.65; Br, 58.0%. **Methyl α : β -dibromo- β -(3-iodophenyl) propionate** (4.0 g) had m.p. 82°-3° (from light petroleum, b.p. 60°-80°) Found: C, 26.9; H, 2.1;

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Br, 37.45 ; I, 28.9. $C_{10}H_9Br_2IO_2$ requires : C, 26.8 ; H, 2.0 ; Br, 35.7 ; I, 28.3%. *Ethyl α : β -dibromo- β -(3-bromo-4-methylphenyl) propionate* (4.5 g) had m.p. 91°-3° (from light petroleum, b.p. 60°-80°) (Found : C, 34.2 ; H, 3.1 ; Br, 56.1. $C_{12}H_{13}Br_2O_2$ requires : C, 33.8 ; H, 3.0 ; Br, 55.9%). *Ethyl α : β -dibromo β -(3-iodo-4-methyl phenyl) propionate* (4.5 g) had m.p. 88-9° (from light petroleum, b. p. 40-60°) (Found : C, 30.35 ; H, 2.9 ; Br, 34.3 ; I, 27.0. $C_{12}H_{13}Br_2IO_2$ requires : C, 30.25 ; H, 2.7 ; Br, 33.6 ; I, 26.7%). *Ethyl α : β -dibromo- β -(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl) propionate* (3.8 g) had m.p. 81°-2° (from light petroleum, b.p. 40°-60°) (Found : C, 37.9 ; H, 3.5 ; Br, 41.4 ; F, 4.7. $C_{12}H_{13}Br_2FO_3$ requires : C, 37.5 ; H, 3.4 ; Br, 41.65 ; F, 4.9%).

β -Arylpropionic Acids. The above powdered dibromo esters (0.01 mol) were added portionwise to 20%

alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (35 ml) at room temperature. When the initial reaction subsided, the mixture was refluxed for 6 hr, the alcohol was evaporated under reduced pressure, and the residue was worked up as usual. The product was then crystallised from a suitable solvent (cf. Table 1).

Self-condensation of β -Arylpropionic Acids. The acid (1.0 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (10 ml) and the solid precipitated after concentration of the solvent was fractionally crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 60°-80°) to give the 6-halogenoanhydrides 8-14). The original mother-liquor was then concentrated, diluted with ether, and allowed to stand in the refrigerator for 24 hr whereby another product crystallised out. This was fractionally crystallised from a suitable solvent to give the 8-halogenoanhydrides (15-19). The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE-1

Compound	M. p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Found C	Found H	X	Formula	Required C	Required H	X
2	157-9 [@] (decomp.)	70	47.6	2.5	35.1	$C_9H_5BrO_2$	48.0	2.2	35.55
3	180-2 ^{@@} (decomp.)	64	39.7	1.85	46.05	$C_9H_5IO_2$	39.7	1.8	46.55
5	174-5 ^{@@} (decomp.)	69	42.4	2.7	44.6	$C_{10}H_7IO_2$	42.0	2.45	44.4
6	156-8 ^{@@} (decomp.)	78	50.6	3.2	33.15	$C_{10}H_7BrO_2$	50.25	2.9	33.4
7	159-61 ^{@@} (decomp.)	60	61.95	3.9	9.8	$C_{10}H_7FO_3$	61.85	3.8	9.8

[@] From light petroleum (b. p. over 120°)
^{@@} From Benzene
X Halogen

TABLE-2

Propi- olic Acid (1.0 g)	Time of reflux (hr)	Pro- duct (°C)	M.p. (°C)	Yield	Ratio	Found C	Found H	X [@]	Formula	Required C	Required H	X [@]
1	1	8	202-3 (B-p)	0.3	3	63.1	2.7	20.35	$C_{18}H_8Cl_2O_8$	63.0	2.35	20.7
			173-5 (B-p)	0.1	1	63.2	2.5	21.2	$C_{18}H_8Cl_2O_8$	63.0	2.35	20.7
2	1	9	213-4 (B-p)	0.35	7	49.8	2.45	37.05	$C_{18}H_8Br_2O_8$	50.0	1.85	37.05
			183-5 (B-p)	0.05	1	49.85	2.1	37.2	$C_{18}H_8Br_2O_8$	50.0	1.85	37.05
3	3	10	253-5 Yellow (B-p)	0.7		41.4	1.8	48.0	$C_{18}H_8I_2O_8$	41.2	1.5	48.1
5	3	12	214-6 Yellow (B-p)	0.7	14	43.5	2.25	44.1	$C_{20}H_{12}I_2O_8$	43.4	2.2	45.65
			247-9 Yellow (p)	0.05	1	—	—	—	$C_{20}H_{12}I_2O_8$	—	—	—
6	3	13	214-6 (B-p)	0.7		52.5	2.9	34.3	$C_{20}H_{12}Br_2O_8$	52.25	2.6	34.8
7	1	14	233-4 Yellow (B)	0.65	Predominant	64.5	3.4	10.3	$C_{20}H_{12}F_2O_8$	64.85	3.25	10.3
			169-70 (B-p)	Trace	—	—	—	—	$C_{20}H_{12}F_2O_8$	—	—	—

(B-p) Benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°).
(p) Light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°).
(B) Benzene
[@] X=Cl for 8 and 15 ; Br for 9, 13 and 16 ; I for 10, 12 and 18 and F for 14 and 19.

Conversion of the anhydrides (8) and (15) into Benzo (c) fluoenones. The finely powdered anhydride (1.0 g) was added portionwise to a stirred solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 g) in dry 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (20 ml) at room temperature during 5 min. The dark reaction mixture was worked out as usual. 3,10-Dichloro-7-oxo-7H-benzo (c) fluorene-6-carboxylic acid (0.8 g) had m. p. 285-7° (orange needles from glacial acetic acid) (Found: C, 63.7; H, 2.4. C₁₈H₈Cl₂O₃ requires: C, 63.0; H, 2.35%). λ_{max} (glacial acetic acid) (nm) 450 ($\epsilon=590$), $\sim 362-4$ ($\epsilon=2400$), and 301 ($\epsilon=41930$). 1,10-Dichloro-7-oxo-7H-benzo (c) fluorene-6-carboxylic acid (0.8 g) had m.p. 315°-7° (red needles from 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane) (Found: C, 63.4; H, 2.5. C₁₈H₈Cl₂O₃ requires: C, 63.0; H, 2.35%). λ_{max} (glacial acetic acid) (nm) 434 ($\epsilon=520$), $\sim 379-82$ ($\epsilon=550$), $\sim 359-61$ ($\epsilon=1,740$), 308 ($\epsilon=75,160$) and 298 ($\epsilon=79,360$).

Thus, 3-halogenophenylpropionic acids (1-3), prepared by the dehydrobromination of the corresponding β -aryl- α : β -dibromopropionic esters,³ were self-condensed with acetic anhydride. 3-Chlorophenyl-propionic acid gave a mixture of anhydrides (yield 40%) from which (8) and (15) were isolated by fractional crystallisation in the ratio 3 : 1, respectively. A nearly similar ratio (2.5 : 1) was also obtained on applying Dewar and Urch spectroscopic mixture analysis method.⁴ Their infrared spectra show strong doublets at 1850 and 1790 and at 1815 and 1760 cm⁻¹ (KBr), respectively ($\nu_{C=O}$ of acid anhydrides)⁵ (cf. Table 3).

However, 3-bromophenylpropionic acid gave a mixture of anhydrides (yield 40%), from which (9) and (16) were isolated in the ratio 7 : 1, respectively, whereas, 3-iodophenylpropionic acid (3), gave only (10). Compounds (8), (9) and (10) were assigned the same structure since they have identical electronic spectra (Fig. 1) which are different from those of compounds (15) and (16) (cf. Table 3 : Fig. 3).

The difference in the ratio of the isomers can be satisfactorily interpreted by a consideration of the size of the halogen atoms. Thus, the increase in the ratio of the 3',6-dihalogenoisomers (8), (9) and (10) on passing from 3-chlorophenylpropionic acid (1) to the 3-iodo derivative (3) is expected and is normal.

The isolation of (11) and (17) in nearly equal amounts on self-condensation of 3-methoxyphenylpropionic acid⁶ (4) indicated that the halogen atom exerts a more steric effect than the methoxy group.

Heating 3-iodo-4-methylphenylpropionic acid (5) with acetic anhydride gave a mixture of anhydrides (12) and (18) in the ratio of 14 : 1, respectively, whereas the 3-bromo-analogue (6) gave only anhydride (13). The infrared spectra of compounds (12), (13) and (18) show strong doublets at 1845, 1845, 1815 and 1780, 1780, 1760 cm⁻¹, respectively ($\nu_{C=O}$ of acid anhydrides)⁵ (cf. Table 3).

TABLE-3

Compd.	I. R. Spectra (cm ⁻¹)		Electronic Spectra					
	$\nu_{C\equiv C}$	$\nu_{C=O}$	λ_{max}/nm	I_{L_b} band ϵ	λ_{max}/nm	I_{L_a} band ϵ	λ_{max}/nm	I_{B_b} band ϵ
(2)	2215							
(3)	2215							
(5)	2210							
(6)	2210							
(7)	2210							
(8)	—	1790, 1850	364 347	3900 4150	323	5110	264 ~257-9	47800 38910
(9)	—	1780, 1845	367 348	6900 5350	326	6390	263	53520
(10)	—	1780, 1845	372 353 337	4630 5250 5280	315	8540	~280-290 269	8640 60490
(12)	—	1780, 1845	371 353	5250 6350	333	7240	270	46130
(13)	—	1780, 1845	368 350	8280 5940	324 ~310-17	7240 6577	269	68730
(14)	—	1775, 1840	~350-360	3720	~310-325	9024	271	55390
(15)	—	1760, 1815	360 341	4520 3150	~312-15 303	7020 7980	266.5 257	64040 54270
(16)	—	1765, 1820	357 338	2630 3770	~294-300	9000	267.5 259.5	82350 64530
(18)	—	1760, 1815	362 344	3940 3400	~305-10	9150	281 ~273-6 ~253-7	49200 41670 22060
(19)	—	1760, 1815	336	9170			273	48310

~ Inflexion

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

The structure assigned to anhydrides (12), (13) and (18) was based on steric consideration and by the similarity of the electronic spectra of (12) and (13) (Fig. 2) and that of (18) (Fig. 3) to those of the corresponding 6-halogeno- and 8-halogeno-7-methoxy-1-(3'-halogeno-4'-methoxyphenyl) naphthalene-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydrides,² respectively. The slight blue shift in the absorption of the former compounds is due to the replacement of the methoxy group by the weaker methyl auxochrome. Furthermore, the lower stretching frequencies of the carbonyl group of (12) and (13) than that of (18) is attributed to a more extended conjugation in compounds (12) and (13) than in (18). This is considered a further evidence for the correctness of the assigned structures.

Fig. 3

On the other hand, when 3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl propiolic acid (7), prepared by dehydrobromination of the corresponding ethyl α : β -dibromo- β -(3-fluoro 4-methoxyphenyl) propionate,³ was selfcondensed in the presence of acetic anhydride, it gave a mixture from which anhydride (14) (predominant) and a trace of anhydride (19) were isolated by fractional crystallisation. Their infrared spectra show strong doublets at 1840 and 1775 cm^{-1} and at 1815 and 1760 cm^{-1} (KBr), respectively, ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of acid anhydrides)⁵ (cf. Table 3). The structure of (14) and (19) was based on steric grounds and by analogy of their electronic spectra with those of the corresponding 6-halogeno-7-methoxy and 8-halogeno-7-methoxy derivatives,² respectively (cf. Table 3; Fig. 4).

The electronic spectra of all these anhydrides absorb in three distinct regions, which correspond to the 1L_b , 1L_a and 1B_b bands of naphthalene. The former band shows the characteristic fine structure (cf. Table 3).

The results obtained in this investigation and in part VII² cannot be explained by a consideration of the size of the halogen atom only, since one should expect the isolation of nearly equal amounts of the two isomeric anhydrides by the self-condensation of 3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenylpropionic acid (7) rather than 3-bromo-4-methoxyphenylpropionic acid. It seems that factors other than the size of the halogen atom must play a role in determining the direction of cyclisation. One of these factors may be the repulsion between the positively charged atom (a) and the positive charge created on the halogen atom by the p- π donor resonance effect, which is expected to be large, since it is demanded by the reaction during the formation of σ -complex (see A and B). This charge may be larger in the case of chlorine than in the case of bromine⁷. Such a repulsion will be larger in the σ -complex (B) than in (A). However, the size of the halogen atom may be the main factor in the case of the iododerivative.

On the other hand, it has been pointed out that chlorine, bromine and iodine may use their d-orbitals for electron acceptor action.⁸ p-d overlap between the unshared electrons of the 2p orbital of the oxygen atom

of the methoxy group and the 3rd orbital of the halogen atom may be possible, especially that the methyl of the methoxy group is forced to orient itself away from the halogen atom to minimise steric interaction. Such an overlap, which is more probable in bromine than in chlorine, may decrease the distance between the methoxy group and the halogen atom, and this exposes carbon atom 'b' to different magnitudes according to the extent of this overlap.

This p-d overlap will also create a partial negative charge on the bromine atom which facilitates the approach of the positively charged carbon atom (a) to carbon atom (b), by lowering the energy of the transient intermediate σ -complex.

This possibility is substantiated by the experimental finding that di-(3-bromo-4-methoxybenzylidene) succinic anhydride gives on cyclisation with sunlight 3', 6-dibromo-4', 7-dimethoxy-1-phenyl naphthalene-2, 3-dicarboxylic anhydride only.⁹ This cyclisation is supposed to take place by a free radical mechanism, and thus no possibility for electrostatic interaction. This conclusion is also supported by the fact that acid (7) in which the fluorine atom has no d-shell, and acid (6) in which the methyl group carries no unshared p-electrons to undergo p-d overlap, gave mainly one isomer. This would also explain, why (2) gave a mixture of anhydrides (10) and (11) in which the former isomer was predominant. A similar overlap involving the d-orbital of the bromine and iodine was considered by Iskander *et al*¹⁰ to be responsible for the stabilisation of α -bromo- and α -iodo-4-nitrobenzyl anions, retarding their α -elimination to 4-nitrophenyl carbenes.

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